

CHOICE OF TREATMENT FOR CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS IN THE BACKGROUND OF ENZYMATIC PANCREATIC INSUFFICIENCY

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Inflammatory-destructive periodontal disease is one of the most complex and common forms of oral pathology. They are the leading cause of tooth loss in the adult population. There is a high frequency of torpid or therapy-resistant forms of periodontitis against the background of enzymatic pancreatic insufficiency [2,7,10].

The mucous membrane of the oral cavity and periodontal tissues in this pathology are exposed to a specific fungal pathology due to the wrong choice of antibiotic therapy, which in turn leads to the development of dysbiosis and immunospecific situations of various origins [1,2,4,17].

The development of periodontitis is often associated with the proliferation of fungi of the genus *Candida*. Simultaneously with the intensive reproduction of fungi and the colonization of the biotope of the periodontal pocket by the fungal flora, activation, increased virulence and reproduction of some types of opportunistic bacteria occur.

Imbalance in microbial associations under such conditions leads to a deficiency of normal microflora [2,6,10,15]. Mutual stimulation of growth and reproduction, increased virulence occurs between fungi and bacteria, which, in conditions of deficiency or elimination of normoflora, contributes to the selection of resistant strains. This explains the resistance of periodontitis associated with *Candida* flora to traditional treatment [3-5,8,9,12,13].

Fungi of the genus *Candida* are adhesive to epithelial cells. Attachment to the mucous membrane is one of the conditions for further invasion of the microorganism into the underlying tissues. A clear correlation was found between the ability of the fungus to adhere and its virulence [1,3,11,14,16,18].

One of the most common localizations of candidal infection is the oral cavity (oropharyngeal candidiasis, oral thrush). Oropharyngeal candidiasis is characterized by damage to the mucous membranes of the cheeks, palate, pharynx, tongue, gums, and corners of the mouth. The disease begins with hyperemia of the mucous membrane, later single or multiple dotted raids of white color appear, more often of a cheesy nature, they can merge, forming larger foci.

The frequency of detection of fungi of the genus *Candida* in parasitocenosis of periodontal pockets is 26.9%. Among patients with chronic generalized periodontitis (GP) associated with *Candida* spp., moderate (51.1%) or severe (29.8%) course of the disease is more often recorded [1,12].

The relevance of optimizing the complex treatment of generalized periodontitis associated with candida infection is obvious [1,4,11,13,16,17,18].

In this regard, the new antimycotic drug flunol is of considerable interest. Flunol®, a representative of triazole agents, is a selective inhibitor of ergosterol synthesis in the fungal membrane. Increases the permeability of the cell membrane, disrupts its growth and replication. Pharmacological effect - fungistatic. It has a highly specific effect on fungal enzymes dependent on cytochrome P450. Flunol* 50 is effective in superficial and systemic fungal infections caused by *Candida* spp., *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Coccidioides immitis*, *Microsporum* spp., *Trichophyton* spp., *Blastomyces dermatitidis*, *Histoplasma capsulatum*.

Purpose of the study. Evaluation of the clinical efficacy of flunol in the complex treatment of chronic periodontitis against the background of pancreatic enzymatic insufficiency.

Material and methods. Patients with generalized periodontitis associated with *Candida* spp. were divided into 2 groups. 32 patients of the 1st group (control) received conventional treatment. 34 patients of the 2nd group (main), along with standard therapy, took flunol at a dose of 50 mg once a day for 14 days.

The condition of periodontal tissues was assessed using the following tests: determination of a simplified hygiene index according to Green - Vermillion (1965); determination of the degree of gum bleeding (Cowell I., 1975), assessment of the papillary-marginal-alveolar index (PMA) (Rappa G., 1960); periodontal index (PI) (Russel A., 1967); measurement of the depth of periodontal pockets (WHO, 1989); determination of pathological tooth mobility (Fleszar T.J. et al., 1980); definition of gingival recession (Miller, 1985).

During a clinical examination, the dental formula, the state of the bite, hard tissues of the teeth, frenulums, the presence of strands, supra- and subgingival dental deposits, the condition of the gum mucosa (edema, hyperemia, bleeding), the nature of the exudate were determined, the presence and depth of periodontal pockets, pathological mobility were determined. teeth.

X-ray examination of the dentoalveolar system included intraoral contact images of individual groups of teeth and orthopantomography.

The generally accepted periodontal treatment consisted in teaching the patient about oral hygiene, sanitation of the oral cavity; professional hygiene; therapeutic treatment (local and general); surgical and orthopedic treatment according to indications.

Functional selective grinding was carried out, alignment of the occlusal surface to exclude traumatic nodes that support inflammation. Elimination of local factors that contribute to the accumulation and activation of the action of the microbial factor (sealing of gingival carious cavities, restoration of interdental contacts).

Antibacterial and anti-inflammatory therapy included rinsing the mouth with a 0.05% solution of chlorhexidine bigluconate 2 times a day after brushing the teeth, metronidazole (Metrogil-dent gel) in the periodontal pocket under a protective fixative bandage, anzibel tablets in the oral cavity, 6-8 tab. per day for 10 days.

Delivery to the laboratory of material for bacteriological examination in order to identify fungi of the genus *Candida* was carried out in a liquid Sabouraud medium, inoculation was carried out on a dense Sabouraud medium. We used standard media manufactured by HiMedia (India). Fungi of the genus *Candida* were identified to a species using commercial chromogenic media HiCrome *Candida* Differential Agar Base, Modified Ml 456A manufactured by HiMedia (India), which allow differentiating the following species by staining and morphology.

The results of the studies were processed by the method of variation statistics with the calculation of the average values (M) and their errors (w), root mean square cutoff (b) and significant differences using Student's t-test (t) at a level of statistical significance of differences (p) not more than 0.05.

Results and discussion. An analysis of patient complaints showed that in chronic periodontitis with identified fungi of the genus *Candida* spp. patients were concerned about dryness and burning in the oral cavity, roughness of the oral mucosa, peeling of the red border of the lips, the presence of cracks in the corners of the mouth and white plaque on the tongue.

A clinical examination of the oral cavity in patients revealed the presence of white plaque on the mucous membrane of the gums and tongue, palatine arches and cheeks. The revealed picture corresponded to chronic hypertrophic candidiasis of the oral mucosa. In some patients with *Candida*-associated periodontitis, infiltration of certain sections of the gingival margin was found in the form of a roller dense to the touch.

In some patients, plaque was not pronounced, but microcracks of the mucous membrane of the tongue and cheeks were determined against the background of a change in the color of the mucous membrane and smoothness of the papillae of the tongue, as well as cracks in the corners of the mouth, which made it possible to establish the diagnosis of chronic atrophic candidiasis of the oral mucosa.

Periodontitis associated with candidal infection had a frequently relapsing course (2-3 times a year or more). Most patients noted only a short-term effect of dental interventions.

Patients complained of pain and bleeding gums, tooth mobility, paresthesia, bad breath, swollen gums. An objective examination revealed swelling, cyanosis of the interdental gingival papillae and marginal gingiva, diffuse inflammatory changes in the gums, hyperemia of the

gingival mucosa involving the transitional fold, bleeding, soreness of the gums, tartar, abundant supra- and subgingival deposits. The depth of periodontal pockets is 3.0-6.0 mm. When pressing the blunt end of the probe on the gum - serous-purulent discharge.

Patients were diagnosed with a predominantly high microbial concentration of *Candida* spp. So, before treatment with *Candida* spp. were recorded in titers less than 6.0 CFU/ml in 46.67-50.0% of patients, and more than 6.0 CFU/ml in 50.0-53.33% (no intergroup differences were found before treatment).

As a result of the therapeutic measures taken in patients with periodontitis associated with *Candida* spp., normalization of oral hygiene indicators, a decrease or complete disappearance of bleeding, thickening of the gingival margin, and a decrease in tooth mobility were observed. The mucous membrane of the gums, tongue, palatine arches and cheeks is pale pink in color, white plaque was not detected. Against the background of treatment, a positive dynamics of indicators of the index assessment of the state of the periodontium was observed.

Analysis of the regression of subjective and objective symptoms of periodontal disease showed that as a result of treatment, a positive effect was achieved in all patients. In the control group, where standard treatment was used, periodontitis remission was recorded in 79.57%, in the main group of patients who received standard periodontitis therapy and an antifungal agent, periodontitis remission was recorded in 100% of cases.

As can be seen from the data presented in Table 1, for all determined tests (hygiene index, PMA, gingival recession, periodontal index, degree of gingival bleeding) in patients with GP associated with *Candida* spp., in the main group after treatment, the indicators were significantly ($p < 0.05$) is closer to normal values than in patients of the control group.

Consequently, the clinical efficacy of the treatment of chronic *Candida*-associated periodontitis was higher in patients who received, along with the basic treatment, the antifungal drug flunol.

Clinical improvement in the state of periodontal tissues, obviously, is mediated both by the eradication of fungal microflora and by the complex therapy of periodontitis. Eradication of *Candida* spp. achieved in all patients of the main group. In patients of the control group, eradication of *Candida* spp. was not so pronounced: after treatment, in 12.07% of patients, the number of microorganisms remained in the titer of more than 6.0 CFU/ml.

Conclusions. Clinical and microbiological observations indicate a more effective eradication of *Candida* spp. when included in the treatment regimen of the antifungal drug flunol.

It can be assumed that the germination of the mycelium of *Candida* spp. leads to damage to the integrity of the epithelial layer and the penetration of periodontal tissues of periodontopathogenic microorganisms. In this regard, the inclusion of the antifungal drug flunol in the complex treatment interrupts the chain of pathological events, which is manifested by a higher clinical efficacy.

The use of the antimycotic agent flunol at a dose of 50 mg once every 14 days increases the effectiveness of the treatment of generalized periodontitis associated with *Candida* spp., significantly improves the clinical, functional and structural state of the periodontium, and contributes to the eradication of *Candida* spp. from periodontal pockets with the achievement and maintenance of disease remission for 6 months.

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